

Green chemistry : A step towards clean and sustainable development[†]

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Introduction

The term "Green Chemistry" was used in 1991 by Paul T. Anastas¹ and it is an environment friendly approach in doing chemistry at laboratory as well as industrial levels. According to Anastas, green chemistry is the utilization of a set of principles that reduces or eliminates the use or generation of hazardous substances in the design, manufacture and application of chemical products. This approach is based on the reduction of the waste at source rather than treating the waste after its formation. Chemists are being blamed for creating pollution but now the approach green chemistry can not only solve the problem of environmental pollution but also provide the way to synthesize and utilize substances in an eco-friendly manner. Green chemistry approach is holistic in nature and encompasses almost all branches of chemical sciences, like synthesis, catalysis, bioorganic, nanochemistry, material science, drug discovery, pharmaceuticals, waste treatment etc. Green chemistry is also termed as clean chemistry, benign by design chemistry², sustainable chemistry³, atom economy, eco-friendly chemistry, and environmentally benign chemistry. To achieve green chemical pathway at laboratory as well as industrial levels is an existing challenge for chemists and to face this challenge, collaborative efforts are needed from government, academic, industries and NGOs.

The green chemical approach is governed by twelve specific principles laid down by Anastas⁴. These prin-

ciples are very significant to combat against environmental pollution and for betterment of human health.

The twelve principles of green chemistry

- (i) **Prevention** : It is better to prevent waste rather than treating or cleaning up waste after it is produced.
- (ii) **Atom economy** : Syntheses should be so designed wherever possible, to maximize the incorporation of all materials used in the process into their final product.
- (iii) **Less hazardous chemical syntheses** : Wherever practicable, synthetic methods should be designed so as to use and generate substances possessing little or no toxicity to human health and the environment.
- (iv) **Designing safer chemicals** : Chemical products should be designed to effect their desired function while minimizing their toxicity.
- (v) **Safer solvents and auxiliaries** : The use of auxiliary substances (e.g. solvents, separating agents etc.) should be made unnecessary, wherever possible and innocuous, when used.
- (vi) **Design for energy efficiency** : Energy requirements of chemical processes should be recognized for their environmental and economic impacts and should be minimized. If possible, syn-

[†]In honour of Professor K. B. Pandeya on the occasion of his 70th Birth Anniversary.

thetic methods should be conducted at ambient temperature and pressure.

- (vii) **Use of renewable feed stocks** : A raw material or feedstock should be renewable rather than depleting, whenever technically and economically practicable or feasible.
- (viii) **Reduce derivatives** : Unnecessary derivatization (use of blocking groups/protection/deprotection, temporary modification of physical/chemical processes) should be minimized or avoided if possible, because such steps require additional reagents and can generate waste.
- (ix) **Catalysis** : Catalytic reagents (as selective as possible) are superior to stoichiometric reagents.
- (x) **Design for degradation** : Chemical products should be designed so that at the end of their function, they break down into innocuous or harmless degradation products and do not persist in the environment.
- (xi) **Real-time analysis for pollution prevention** : Analytical methodologies need to be further developed to allow for real-time, in-process monitoring and control prior to the formation of hazardous substances.
- (xii) **Inherently safer chemistry for accident prevention** : Substances and the form of a substance used in chemical process should be chosen to minimize the potential for chemical accidents, including releases of chemicals, explosions and fires.

The most advantageous way of carrying out a chemical synthesis is by applying these principles of green chemistry such that the by products are either minimized or eliminated. Chemical processes can be made "Green" by choosing green substrates, green reagents, green catalysts, green solvents, green condition etc. To design a green chemical synthesis, the following considerations are to be kept in view.

Green substrates

It is quite necessary to consider that the starting material for any chemical process should be harmless to environment and human health as well as renewable. Therefore, it is significant to avoid the use of petrochemical as

starting material. Alternative starting material of biological/agricultural origin may be chosen to make the synthesis green, like acetic acid, mannitol, glue, levulinic acid, furan, alcohols etc. Large amounts of adipic acid are utilized each year for production of nylon, polyurethanes, lubricants and plasticizers but for the synthesis of adipic acid, benzene is the starting material, which is a well known carcinogen. Green chemical approach philosophy has changed the minds of chemists that instead of benzene, glucose may be chosen as starting material to get adipic acid using genetically modified bacteria⁵. A green starting material for electrophilic aromatic substitution has been developed by Burtch and Wilson⁶.

Green reagents

Reagents used in chemical syntheses should be such that they are quite efficient, selective, innocuous and easily available. Traditionally, for methylation reaction, the methylating reagent used is methyl halide or methyl sulfate, which are toxic with negative environmental impact.

Dimethyl carbonate (DMC) is a good green chemical alternative as methylating reagent, which is less harmful to human health and environment as well as selective. It has been used as eco-friendly substitute for dimethyl sulfate (DMS). The reactions of DMC with reactive methylene compounds produces monomethylated derivative with selectivity^{7,8} (with no inorganic salt produced).

Dibenzyl carbonate (DBC) also exhibits similar reactivity and, selectivity for monobenzylating methylene active compounds^{9,10}.

A group of reagents, called polymer supported reagents, are also in use as green reagents. In these reagents, the main reagent is bound to a polymer support. The advantage of using such reagents is recovery of excess reagent by filtration, which can be reused again. Also, the isolation of the product is relatively easy, e.g. polymer supported per acids for epoxidation¹¹, polymer supported chromic acid as an oxidant¹², polymeric

thioanisoyl resin for selective oxidation of alcohols¹³, poly-*N*-bromosuccinimide (PNBS) for selection bromination¹⁴, etc.

Green solvents

In industries, volatile organics (VOCs) are used as solvents for synthesis of various useful chemical products. These organic solvents are harmful to human health as well as creating pollution in the environment (workers, employee of the chemical units face serious health hazards). Therefore, it is necessary to search solvents which are stable, non-polluting and non-hazardous to human health. Further it is said that the best solvent is no solvent and solvent free organic synthesis (dry media reactions) has attracted the attention of chemists worldwide but in absence of solvent, thermal runs aways and handling of undissolved materials are the two main problems and many reactions can not be carried out in solvent free processes. Therefore, search for green, greener and greenest solvents for various organic syntheses is still going on. Three useful and important green solvents have found their applications in various industrial processes. (i) Ionic liquids (ILs), (ii) Supercritical fluids (SCFs) and (iii) Fluorous compounds (fluorous phase reaction). Other include lactate esters, miceller systems etc.

Ionic liquids

Ionic liquids are the substances composed of cations and anions. They are liquid at or close to room temperature. Ionic liquids have emerged as green solvents because they have no measurable vapour pressure and that a wide range of chemical reactions can be performed in them. They are non-volatile and thermally stable. Their polarity, hydrophobicity and solvent miscibility behaviors could be easily tuned through appropriate modification of cations and anions and that's why they are also termed as "designer solvents". The field of ionic liquids has been excellently reviewed by Welton¹⁵, Holbrey and Sedden¹⁶ and Sedden¹⁷. Commonly used ionic liquids are those with alkylammonium, alkylphosphonium, *N*-alkylpyridinium and *N,N'*-dialkylimidazolium cation and Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, PF₆⁻, BF₄⁻, NO₃⁻, chloroaluminate (AlCl₄)⁻, acetate (ACO)⁻, trifluoroacetate (TA)⁻, trifluoromethanesulfate or triflate (OTf)⁻, etc. as anions. Ionic liquids find their useful and important applications from hydrogenation to biocatalytic reactions¹⁸.

SCFs

Another important green solvents are supercritical fluids. These are produced by heating a gas above its critical temperature or compressing a liquid above its critical pressure. SCFs have both; the gaseous property with high diffusivity and liquid property of dissolution. These properties make SCFs efficient extraction solvents with high mass transfer properties¹⁹. SCFs are highly selective, recyclable, non-toxic and economically competitive; however, safety risk of high operating pressures is to be taken care of²⁰. Supercritical carbon dioxide, scCO₂ (31.1 °C, 73.8 bar) is the most commonly used green solvent due to its low critical temperature and pressure, low cost and non-toxic nature. However, several other SCFs are also in use in industrial processes. Besides, CO₂, supercritical water, scH₂O (374 °C, 218 atm) is another commonly used SCF. scH₂O is an excellent green solvent for organic reactions and very poor solvent for inorganic salts. This affords to extract both; inorganic and organic compounds. Biodiesel production from the algal lipids extracted with scCO₂ shows a great potential²¹. Supercritical CO₂ has also been cited as an effective medium for a novel conversion of glycerol and alcohols in the heterogeneous telomerization of butadiene²².

Others

Liquid polymers²³, fluorous solvents²⁴, eutectic mixtures etc. have the potential to be used as green solvents. So whenever one wants to chose a green solvent, the order is : No solvent > Water (room temperature) > scCO₂/scH₂O > ionic liquids > lactate esters > fluorous solvents. Water is called the greenest liquid solvent because of its abundant availability, non-toxic, non-flammable, environmentally benign nature and its unique reactivity as well as selectivity.

Green catalysts

Conventional catalysts are hazardous, corrosive and toxic in nature and, therefore, it is pertinent to use green catalyst, which is environmentally benign and non-hazardous to human health as well as has maximum selectivity for the product formation. As one knows that catalysis is the engine that drives the development of chemistry and industry, causing sustainable development of any country. It is a matter of great concern for chemists to

develop new green catalysts for various useful chemical processes. Now a days, conventional acid catalyst. HF has been replaced by fluoride silica-alumina catalyst for production of linear alkyl benzene. Zeolites, clayzic, titanium silicates, vanadium silicates, biocatalysts²⁵, phase transfer catalysts²⁶, photocatalysts²⁷, polymer supported catalysts²⁸ etc. are among other green catalysts.

In traditional chemical synthesis, the stoichiometric amount of reagents and high loading of catalysts were required but according to green chemistry protocol to achieve atom efficiency, it is the need of the day that instead of stoichiometric amount, one should use catalytic amount of reagents and green catalysts. Catalysis has remained a very intensive field of research in last two decades because of environmental regulations imposed on chemical and pharmaceutical industries. A rapid growth in this field has changed the process engineering of various chemical industries. Hazardous catalysts (homogeneous) have been replaced by heterogeneous green catalysts in various industrial processes. Use of mesoporous solid acid green catalysts based on silica and zirconia in many important reactions have reduced the environmental pollution and health hazards²⁹. An alternate approach to utilize mesoporous solid in liquid phase selective oxidation reactions is to use solid per acids. Also, it is possible to prepare heterogeneous analogs of most of the commonly used soluble and homogeneous catalysts by chemical surface modification³⁰.

Palladium is highly versatile metal for organic synthesis and it can be effectively immobilized on chemically modified mesoporous material that provides the right ligand geometry. These have been used in important reactions like carbon-carbon bond forming Heck and Suzuki reaction³¹. Iron-porphyrins are highly specific catalysts for oxidation and electron transfer reactions. The enantioselective hydrogenation of alkene as a model for new enantioselective catalysts has been demonstrated³². Fe-TAML (tetra amido macrocyclic ligand) has been synthesized as environmentally safe oxidative catalyst that can be used to decontaminate biological weapons like anthrax and eliminate toxic residues produced by several industries³³. Enantioselective organocatalysis is an emerging area in asymmetric synthesis, which is a powerful synthetic paradigm, complementary to metal catalysed transformation. Proline catalysed intramolecular aldol process

is a good example. Chitosan is a green catalyst for synthesis of pyridazines and fused pyridazines; thus, replacing piperidine and pyridine, the hazardous conventional catalysts³⁴. Biocatalysts have also shown their potential for green chemical synthesis³⁵. Use of nanoparticles in catalysis has recently drawn the attention of scientific community all over the world and future aspect of green nanotechnology have been discussed^{36,37}.

Green chemistry and green technologies for sustainable development

Green chemistry has entered in our daily life activities also, e.g. in laundry, the cleaning of cloths is being done by liquids carbon dioxide replacing the traditional use of harmful and carcinogenic PERC (perchloroethylene, $\text{Cl}_2\text{C}=\text{CCl}_2$). For bleaching of papers, bath of NaOH and Na_2S or chlorine gas was used but now a days, chlorine dioxide, hydrogen peroxide, ozone, etc. are used for bleaching purposes.

Green chemistry is enjoying significant adoption by industries all around the world and widespread activity is there in the research community. This is because of the fact that green chemistry not only addresses the fundamental scientific challenges of protecting human health and the environment at the molecular level but also accomplishes this in an economically beneficial manner for industry. But the greatest challenge in the field of green chemistry is to follow the green protocol in actual practice. However, the growing awareness of the pressing demand for greener and more sustainable technologies has focused attention on the use of atom efficient catalytic methodologies for the manufacture of fine chemicals and pharmaceuticals^{38,39}. Liquid-liquid biphasic catalysis provides an industrially attractive method for the recovery and recycling of catalysts as an alternative to the traditional solid heterogeneous catalysts. Water as greenest solvent has also attracted the attention of synthetic organic chemists in recent years and green chemistry oriented organic synthesis in water have been accomplished⁴⁰. The importance of green chemistry in processes research, development and evaluating the greenness of chemical processes and products in the pharmaceutical industries have been investigated^{41,42}. Recently, asymmetric catalysis in solvent free and highly concentrated reactants, catalyzed reactions in ionic liquids, catalysed reactions in

SCFs and catalysed reactions in water have gained much attention by organic chemists all over the globe⁴³⁻⁶⁴

Incorporating the green chemistry principles in the development of green and sustainable technologies, the present research have started showing their signatures in various fields, like photocatalysis⁶⁵⁻⁶⁸, sonocatalysis and microwave technology⁶⁹. These are termed as advanced oxidation processes or advanced oxidation technologies (AOPs or AOTs). Dye-sensitized nanocrystalline solar cells^{70,71}, bioorganic catalysis⁷², biomass conversion to selected chemicals^{73,74}, eco-friendly H₂-production⁷⁵, plastics from carbon dioxide⁷⁶, pollutant degradation technologies⁷⁶, biofuels⁷⁷, etc.

Photocatalysis

The use of semiconducting oxides as photocatalyst for degradation of pollutants has attracted the attention of scientific community all over the world because it is an efficient and eco-friendly process. Photocatalytic degradation was found to be the most promising process for waste water treatment in which the semiconductor particles act as photocatalysts or short-circuited microelectrodes on excitation.

The chemical reaction that occurs in the presence of a semiconductor and light are called 'Photocatalytic reaction' and the term "Photocatalysis" is still reserved for such reactions only. "Photocatalyst" is defined as a species, which induces some photochemical reactions. It is a process in which semiconducting material is exposed to light and as a result, an electron-hole pair is generated. The electron in the conduction band can be used for reducing substrate whereas the hole in the valence band may be utilized for oxidation purposes. The generally used photocatalysts are binary chalcogenides e.g. ZnO, ZnS, TiO₂, CdS, etc.

The band gap in semiconductors ranges from 1.5 to 3.0 eV depending upon the nature of semiconductor. This much energy (normally provided by exposure to light) is sufficient to excite an electron from the valence band to the conduction band.

The photocatalytic reactions are classified into two categories :

(a) Homogeneous photocatalysis – In which, the substrate and photocatalyst, both exist in the same phase.

(b) Heterogeneous photocatalysis – In which, both the substrate and the photocatalyst exist in different phases. Semiconductor powders are quite commonly used in this type of photocatalytic reactions.

When an electron is excited from the valence band of the semiconductor to its conduction band (by the absorption of light corresponding to its band gap), a hole is left behind in the valence band. In all, there are four possible combinations of semiconductor and substrate, depending upon relative positions of bands of semiconductors and redox levels of substrates, respectively. These are :

(a) If the redox level of substrate is lower than the conduction band of semiconductor, then the electron will flow from semiconductor to substrate smoothly. It results into reduction of the substrate.

(b) If the redox level of the substrate is higher than the valence band of the semiconductor, then the hole will be transferred to the substrate molecules. It results into oxidation of the substrate.

(c) If the redox level of the substrate is lower than conduction band and higher than the valence band, then both; oxidation and reduction of the substrate will take place, and

(d) If the redox level of the substrate is higher than conduction band and lower than the valence band of the substrate, then neither oxidation nor reduction of substrate will take place.

Heterogeneous photocatalytic decomposition of phenol over TiO₂ powder was studied by Okamoto *et al.*⁷⁸. The products at initial stage were hydroquinone, catechol, 1,2,4-benzenetriol, pyrogallol and 2-hydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone, which underwent further photocatalytic oxidation via acids and/or aldehydes, finally to CO₂ and H₂O. Kawaguchi⁷⁹ also reported a similar reaction.

Harada *et al.*⁸⁰ studied the photocatalytic degradation of trichlorophenol over Pt-loaded TiO₂ semiconductor whereas Sehili *et al.*⁸¹ investigated the photocatalytic transformation of chloroaromatic derivatives such as chlorophenol and dichlorobenzenes on ZnO involving the formation of adduct between •OH radicals and aromatic compounds whereas Castrants and Gibilisco⁸² observed the effect of pH on the rate of degradation of phenol.

Photocatalytic oxidation of phenol in the presence of H₂O₂ and TiO₂ powder was observed by Wieg *et al.*⁸³.

Yanagida *et al.*⁸⁴ used ZnS nanocrystalline catalyzed photo-oxidation of organic compound. Photoinduced formation of electron on nanocrystalline ZnS will be responsible for reduction of water to hydrogen. The photoformed hole oxidizes aliphatic amines, alcohols and some alkylated aromatic compounds.

Pak and Kharangi⁸⁵ investigated photocatalytic oxidation of phenol in aqueous dispersion of CdS fixed on silica carriers while Claudia *et al.*⁸⁶ reported the efficient photocatalytic degradation of *p*-nitrophenol and acid orange-7 using ZnS nanocrystals (~3 to 5 nm diameter) with 50% product yield. The degradation of acid orange-7 was suggested to occur via an oxidative pathway involving hydroxyl radical formed at the photocatalyst/liquid interface. Kang *et al.*⁸⁷ observed photocatalytic degradation of 4-chlorophenol in water and comparatively examined it with TiO₂ powder and TiO₂/CdS powder.

Neppolian *et al.*⁸⁸ studied photodegradation of some textile dyes over ZnO while photocatalytic degradation of cationic dyes by TiO₂/bentonite nanocomposite was carried out by Sun *et al.*⁸⁹. Visible light induced photodegradation of organic pollutants on dye adsorbed TiO₂ surface has been investigated by Mahata and Chatterjee⁹⁰. Photocatalytic transformation of acid orange-20 and Cr^{VI} in aqueous TiO₂ suspension was studied by Papadam *et al.*⁹¹. Chen *et al.*⁹² observed photocatalytic degradation of dye pollutants on silica gel supported TiO₂ particles under visible light irradiation while Morwetz and Selli⁹³ investigated the effect of iron species in photocatalytic degradation of azo dyes in TiO₂ suspension.

Photocatalytic degradation of chlorobenzoic acid (CBA) isomers in aqueous suspension of modified titania was studied by Tahiri *et al.*⁹⁴. The three isomers of CBA disappeared from water in the order of 3-CBA < 2-CBA < 4-CBA. The chemisorption of CBA molecule involves the carboxylic group linked to the surface with the aromatic ring possibly oriented perpendicular to the surface. A mechanism has been proposed for this reaction by Ogawa⁹⁵. The OH group of titania was spontaneously renewed by dissociation of chemisorbed water.

A novel route for waste water treatment involving degradation of naphthol green-B was reported by Kumar *et al.*⁹⁶ whereas photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes on visible light by PbBiO₂Br photocatalyst was carried

out by Shan *et al.*⁹⁷. Photocatalytic removal of hazardous dye cyanosine from industrial waste using TiO₂ was studied by Jain and Shrivastava⁹⁸. Jiang *et al.*⁹⁹ observed the solar photocatalytic decolorization of basic blue-41 in an aqueous suspension of TiO₂-ZnO. Ibadon *et al.*¹⁰⁰ studied the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ foam and surface modified binary oxide titania nanoparticles. Lhomme *et al.*¹⁰¹ studied the photocatalytic removal of pesticides in pure water and commercial agriculture solution on TiO₂ coated media. They carried out the degradation of chlortoluron and cyprocozole pesticides.

A lot of work has been carried out in the field of photocatalysis proving its significant role in the development of green chemistry. A number of scientists have made attempts to use some semiconductors as photocatalyst to remove toxic organic and inorganic contaminants from waste water¹⁰²⁻¹⁰⁵. The photocatalytic degradation of lissamine fast yellow has been carried out in the aqueous suspension of ZnO under artificial light by Pare *et al.*¹⁰⁶. ZnO degrades this dye effectively in the presence of both; artificial and sunlight. Photocatalytic degradation of orange-G over ZnO in presence of surfactants was studied by Ameta *et al.*¹⁰⁷. Chakrabarti and Dutta¹⁰⁸ used ZnO for photodegradation of methylene blue and eosin. A complete removal of colour was achieved in this case.

Mansoori *et al.*¹⁰⁹ used zinc oxide and lead oxide as photocatalyst for the photocatalytic bleaching of rhodamine-B and rhodamine-6G. Photocatalytic degradation of azo dye using ZnO as a photocatalyst has been investigated by Daheshvar *et al.*¹¹⁰ whereas photobleaching of amaranth dye in presence of ZnO photocatalyst was reported by Kothari *et al.*¹¹¹. Jingfeng *et al.*¹¹² synthesized nitrogen doped ZnO by grinding and heating ZnO-urea mixture. Its high photocatalytic activity in an anti-bacterial test was also reported. Height *et al.*¹¹³ used Ag-ZnO catalyst for photodegradation of methylene blue in UV range. The catalyst was prepared from flame spray photolysis.

Recently, some work has been carried out in the field of nanosized photocatalysts¹¹⁴⁻¹¹⁶. Now, researchers have developed an interest in the nano-ZnO and a number of methods have been applied to synthesize nano-ZnO with greater efficiency and effective working range. The waste water treatment by photocatalytic oxidation in presence of nano-ZnO has been observed by Meng and Juan¹¹⁷.

Liao *et al.*¹¹⁸ prepared nanosized TiO₂/ZnO composite catalyst and studied its photocatalytic activity for the degradation of methyl orange. UV induced photocatalytic degradation of azo dyes by organic-capped ZnO nanocrystals immobilized on to substrates has been reported by Comparelli *et al.*¹¹⁹. Photocatalytic bleaching of eosin using zinc oxide and effect of surface charge was investigated by Vyas *et al.*¹²⁰ while photocatalytic bleaching of Evans blue over zinc oxide was observed by Kothari *et al.*¹²¹.

Villasenor *et al.*¹²² reported the photocatalytic degradation of organic matter dissolved in Kraft Black liquor which is an important effluent from pulp and paper industries. Punjabi *et al.*¹²³ studied the photoreduction of congo red by ascorbic acid and EDTA as reductant and cadmium sulphide as photocatalyst. Kothari *et al.*¹²⁴ also carried out photodegradation of malachite green and observed that photocorrosion of CdS is also controlled under these conditions.

Photo-Fenton reactions

The globe is facing an ecological imbalance and thus, there is a growing concern about conserving this ecological balance using some eco-friendly or green chemical pathways. Photochemical reactions may prove to be an important tool in achieving the green and clean world in years to come. In recent years, photochemical methods for the destruction of organic pollutants in waste water have been developed.

The reactions carried out in light either in the presence or absence of oxygen, but involving oxidation are known as "Photooxidation reactions". When an organic substrate and molecular oxygen reacts, it leads to the formation of free radicals and radical coupling products.

A search is still on for an alternative method of treating waste water with such active species so that the water is not further polluted after the removal or degradation of pollutants. Here, Fenton's reagent enters the scene. The Fenton reaction was discovered by Fenton¹²⁵. The hydroxyl radical is an active species, which attacks and destroys the undesired compounds. The Fenton reaction produces hydroxyl radicals by interaction of H₂O₂ with ferrous salts.

In dark, the reaction is retarded after complete conversion of all the Fe²⁺ to Fe³⁺. It has been found that

illumination of the Fe²⁺-Fe³⁺-H₂O₂ system increases the degradation rate of many organic substances and it is known as photo-Fenton reaction.

Forty years later after the discovery of Fenton reaction, its mechanism was postulated¹²⁶. The Fenton reaction can be outlined as follows :

where M is a transition metal such as Fe or Cu. During the reaction, Fe³⁺ ions are accumulated in the system and after all the Fe²⁺ ions are consumed, the reaction practically stops. Photochemical regeneration of ferrous ions (Fe²⁺) by photoreduction of ferric ions (Fe³⁺), was proposed by Faust and Hoigne¹²⁷. The newly generated ferrous ions reacts with H₂O₂ generating a second •OH radical and ferric ion, and the cycle continues.

Chamarro and Esplugas¹²⁸ used the Fenton process for the degradation of phenol, 4-chlorophenol, 2,4-dichlorophenol and nitrobenzene. The process was found to eliminate toxic substances and to increase the biodegradability of the treated water. Kaludjerski¹²⁹ confirmed that dichlorodiethyl ether's biodegradability can be enhanced by modified Fenton's reagent. Some work about the treatment of textile water by means of Fenton and photo-Fenton processes has been carried out and most of them showed their effectiveness for color removal and COD reduction¹³⁰⁻¹³².

Zepp *et al.*¹³³ and Safarzadeh-Amiri *et al.*¹³⁴ reported an improvement of photo-assisted Fenton process in the UV-Vis/ferrioxalate/H₂O system, which has been recently demonstrated to be more efficient than photo-Fenton reaction for the abatement of organic pollutants. Recently, two new electrochemical procedures for the detoxification of acidic waste waters (the so called electro-Fenton and photoelectron-Fenton process, where H₂O₂ is electrogenerated) have been developed and these have shown their good efficiencies for the mineralization of aniline¹³⁵, 4-chlorophenol¹³⁶ and 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid¹³⁷.

Many carboxylic acids have been degraded by the photo-Fenton process. Benitez *et al.*¹³⁸ reported the degradation of gallic acid (3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acid) in aqueous solution by UV/H₂O₂ treatment, Fenton's reagent and the photo-Fenton system. Solar photodegradation

of dichloroacetic acid and 2,4-dichlorophenol using an enhanced photo-Fenton process was carried out by Nogueira *et al.*¹³⁹. The photo-assisted Fenton degradation of salicylic acid, using strongly acidic ion exchange resin (SAIER) exchanged with Fe ions as catalyst, in the presence of UV light (254 nm) and H₂O₂ was studied by Feng *et al.*¹⁴⁰. Oxalic acid destruction by combined heterogeneous photolysis and photo-Fenton reaction using UV/Fe/H₂O₂ and the UV/TiO₂/Fe/H₂O₂ was studied by Quici *et al.*¹⁴¹.

Photo-Fenton assisted ozonation of *p*-coumaric acid present in olive oil mill waste water was investigated by Monteagudo *et al.*¹⁴² while the changes in the molecular and structural characteristics of humic acid during photo-Fenton processes were studied by Fukushima *et al.*¹⁴³. Degradation of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) using both, Fenton reagent and cobalt-porphyrin monosulfate (Co/PMS) in dark and under solar radiation in photo-assisted AOPs has been investigated by Bandala *et al.*¹⁴⁴. Vaeghese *et al.*¹⁴⁵ studied the degradation of cyanuric acid with a combination of gamma radiolysis and Fenton reaction.

Degradations of a number of nitro compounds including many explosives were carried out by the use of photo-Fenton reaction. Photocatalytic and Fenton oxidation of 5-nitro-1,2,4-triazol-3-one (NTO) in aqueous suspension of TiO₂ was studied by Campion *et al.*¹⁴⁶. Fenton reagent, UV/H₂O₂ and UV/Fenton's reagent were used to mineralize dinitrotoluenes and trinitrotoluene of spent acid in toluene nitration process^{147,148}. The combined Fenton and biological flow reactor degradation of *p*-nitrotoluene-*ortho*-sulphonic acids (*p*-NTS) has been reported by Kiwi *et al.*¹⁴⁹. 2,4-Dinitrotoluene has also been degraded by photo-Fenton process¹⁵⁰. The degradation of four nitrophenols namely 2-nitrophenol, 4-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol and 2,4,6-trinitrophenol with Fenton process, solar and UV assisted Fenton processes were investigated by Kavitha and Palanivelu¹⁵¹, Lie *et al.*¹⁵² and Kiwi *et al.*¹⁵³.

A kinetic study on the degradation of *p*-nitroaniline by Fenton oxidation process has been reported by Sun *et al.*¹⁵⁴. Oxidation of the nitro aromatic explosives namely, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, ammonium picrate, 2,4-dinitrotoluene, 2,4,6-trinitrotoluene (TNT) and hexahydro-

1,3,5-trinitro-1,3,5-triazine (RDX) by Fenton's reagent has also been investigated¹⁵⁵⁻¹⁵⁸.

The oxidative degradation of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) by the photochemically enhanced Fenton reaction was observed by Braun *et al.*¹⁵⁹ and photo-Fenton process was studied by Guardani *et al.*¹⁶⁰. Winery waste waters, being seasonal and experiencing substantial flow variations, are difficult to treat by conventional biological process. The photo-Fenton reaction in homogeneous and heterogeneous phase was studied for the treatment of this waste water by Ovellerio *et al.*¹⁶¹ and Mosteo *et al.*¹⁶², respectively.

Photo-Fenton reaction is widely used for the degradation of phenol in waste water. This degradation was studied by Pena *et al.*¹⁶³ in concentrated waste waters. Maciel *et al.*¹⁶⁴ reported phenol removal from high salinity effluent using Fenton reagent and photo-Fenton reaction. Heterogeneous photo-Fenton degradation of phenolic aqueous solution over iron containing SBA-15 catalyst was carried out by Melero *et al.*¹⁶⁵. The application of AOPs, dark Fenton and photo-assisted Fenton type processes; Fe²⁺/H₂O₂, Fe³⁺/H₂O₂, UV/Fe²⁺/H₂O₂, UV/Fe³⁺/H₂O₂ and UV/Fe⁰/H₂O₂, for degradation of phenol as model organic pollutant in the waste water was investigated by Selanec *et al.*¹⁶⁶. The degradation kinetics and mechanism of phenol in photo-Fenton type processes; Fe²⁺/H₂O₂, Fe³⁺/H₂O₂, UV/Fe²⁺/H₂O₂, UV/Fe³⁺/H₂O₂ and UV/Fe⁰/H₂O₂, and Fe⁰/H₂O₂ was carried out by Lei and He¹⁶⁷.

The role of ferrous ion in Fenton and photo-Fenton processes for the degradation of phenol was studied by Kavitha and Palanivelu¹⁶⁸ and Sengul *et al.*¹⁶⁹. Tryba *et al.*¹⁷⁰ investigated the mechanism of phenol decomposition of Fe-C-TiO₂ and the effect of the carbon coating of Fe-C-TiO₂ irradiation via photo-Fenton process was studied by Toyoda *et al.*¹⁷¹. Molina *et al.*¹⁷² suggested the iron species incorporated over different silica support for the heterogeneous photo-Fenton oxidation of phenol. Photo-Fenton treatment of water containing natural phenolic pollutants like vanillin, protocatechuric acid, syringic acid, *p*-coumaric acid, gallic acid and L-tyrosine was reported by Malato *et al.*¹⁷³. Photo-Fenton and photodegradation of bisphenol-A in aqueous solution with iron oxides was investigated by Li *et al.*¹⁷⁴ and Katsumata *et*

*al.*¹⁷⁵. Role of intermediate in the degradation of 4-chlorophenol, 4-nitrophenol and phenol by Fenton process was investigated by Yingxun *et al.*¹⁷⁶ and degradation of ethylene glycol and crysols in photo-Fenton system has also been reported^{177,178}.

Sonochemistry

It is a branch of chemical science dealing with the chemical effects and applications of ultrasonic waves, that is, sound with frequencies above 20 kHz that lies beyond the upper limits of human hearing. Sonochemistry is the application of ultrasound energy to chemical reactions. The progress of sonochemistry in green and sustainable chemistry is dependent upon the possibility of scaling up the excellent laboratory results for industrial use. There are currently several systems commercially available with configurations to suit most of the industrial applications. Ultrasound is transmitted through a medium using pressure waves by inducing vibrational motion of the molecule, which alternately compress and stretch the molecular structure of medium due to time varying pressure. If the intensity of ultrasound is increased in a liquid, a point is reached, where the intramolecular forces are not able to hold the molecular structure intact. Consequently, it breaks down and cavitation bubbles are created. This process is called cavitation and the point, where it starts is known as the cavitation threshold¹⁷⁹.

Chemical transformation by ultrasound does not come from direct coupling of sound field with chemical species but from the phenomena of cavitation and the violent collapse of bubbles, leading to the temperature to several thousand of Kelvin, pressure to one thousand atmosphere and cooling rates above 10^{10} K/s. In such extreme conditions, water dissociation takes place to generate some oxidants like hydroxyl radical, hydrogen peroxide, ozone etc., which are responsible for various chemical reactions referred to as sonochemical reactions¹⁸⁰⁻¹⁸².

Ultrasound in synthetic organic chemistry

The following sonochemical effects can be observed in chemical reactions and processes :

- (i) Increase in reaction speed,
- (ii) Increase in reaction output,
- (iii) More efficient energy usage,

- (iv) Sonochemical methods for switching of reaction pathway,
- (v) Performance improvement of phase transfer catalysts,
- (vi) Avoidance of phase transfer catalysts,
- (vii) Use of crude or technical reagents,
- (viii) Activation of metals and solids,
- (ix) Increase in the reactivity of reagents or catalysts,
- (x) Improvement of particle synthesis and
- (xi) Coating of nanoparticles.

There are two types of effects mediated by ultrasound : chemical and physical. When the quantity of bubbles is low, it is mainly the physical rate acceleration that plays a role. The chemical effects of ultrasound are diverse and include dramatic improvement in stoichiometric and catalytic reactions¹⁸³. Solids made from nanometer sized components often exhibit properties distinct from those of the bulk, in part because clusters have electronic structures with a high density of states, but not yet continuous bands¹⁸⁴⁻¹⁸⁶.

Applications of sonochemistry can be found in many areas, but sonochemical processes are most widely developed for heterogeneous reactions. It is a multidisciplinary field in which chemists, physicists and chemical engineers must cooperate to develop a better understanding of the processes that take place within the collapsing bubbles so as to develop totally new applications. However, the potential for making improvements in many types of reaction suggests that every chemical laboratory should be equipped with at least one cleaning bath for simple trials¹⁸⁷. β -Amino- α,β -unsaturated esters were produced by a sonochemical Blaise reaction of nitriles, zinc powder, zinc oxide and ethyl bromoacetate in THF in a commercial ultrasonic cleaning bath¹⁸⁸.

A palladium-catalyzed and ultrasonic promoted Sonogashira coupling/1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of acid chlorides, terminal acetylenes, and sodium azide was studied by Li *et al.*¹⁸⁹. Hemantha *et al.*¹⁹⁰ described a facile one-pot procedure for the synthesis of urea-linked peptidomimetics and neoglycopeptides under Curtius rearrangement conditions and ultrasonication.

1,4-Dihydropyridine and polyhydroquinoline derivatives were synthesized in excellent yields in aqueous micelles. The reaction was catalyzed by PTSA and strongly accelerated by ultrasonic irradiation¹⁹¹. An ultrasound assisted preparation of a series of ambient temperature ionic liquids, 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium (AMIM) halides, which proceeds via efficient reaction of 1-methylimidazole with alkyl halides/terminal dihalides under solvent free conditions was described¹⁹².

Hasin and Wu¹⁹³ reported the sonochemical synthesis of copper(I) hydride (CuH) by the ultrasonic irradiation of a copper(II) aqueous solution. A convenient sonochemical method was suggested for the preparation of polystyrene functionalized graphenes starting from graphite flakes and a reactive monomer, styrene¹⁹⁴. Methods of synthesis of highly dispersed inorganic materials based on the use of ultrasonic treatment were developed by Baranchikov *et al.*¹⁹⁵. Ultrasound assisted synthesis of aliphatic acid esters at room temperature have been reported by Hobuss *et al.*¹⁹⁶.

Zbancioc *et al.*¹⁹⁷ described an efficient synthesis of spiro derivatives using ultrasonic irradiation. Ultrasound assisted synthesis of unsymmetrical biaryls by Stille cross-coupling reactions have been studied by Domini *et al.*¹⁹⁸. Efficient one-pot three-component synthesis of *N*-(4-arylthiazol-2-yl)hydrazones in water under ultrasound irradiation was reported by Zhang *et al.*¹⁹⁹. Saleh *et al.*²⁰⁰ reported ultrasound promoted synthesis of some novel fused pyrans, while Rajesh *et al.*²⁰¹ suggested ultrasound promoted synthesis of novel bipodal and tripodalpiperidin-4-ones and silica chloride mediated conversion to its piperidin-4-ols.

The Grignard reaction is one of the most common synthetic pathways in organic chemistry and has been used widely in the preparation of fine chemicals and phar-

maceutical intermediates. Cravotto *et al.*²⁰² demonstrated that ultrasound assisted Grignard reactions are safe, efficient and reproducible. Sonochemical degradation of bisphenol-A in aqueous solution, which can cause several damages for humans, animals and the environment, was investigated at different ultrasonic intensities under air atmosphere²⁰³. Sonochemical engineering is a field involving the application of sonic and ultrasonic waves to chemical processing. Sonochemistry enhances or promotes chemical reactions and mass transfer. It offers the potential for shorter reaction cycles, cheaper reagents, and less extreme physical conditions, leading to less expensive and perhaps smaller plants. Environmental sonochemistry is a rapidly growing area that deals with the destruction of organics in aqueous solutions²⁰⁴.

Despite the ever increasing usage of ultrasound to enhance reactivity in synthetic chemistry, many chemists experience difficulty in reproducing the work of other groups. Although such problems are most commonly encountered with chemical reactions which have been performed in ultrasonic baths; even reactions involving probe systems have sometimes proved difficult to reproduce. Mason *et al.*²⁰⁵ reported the results of some model reactions using the newly developed Undatim sonoreactor probe system. Using this facility, they were able to report how ultrasonic energy input to a chemical reaction was affected by the following important reaction parameters : ultrasonic power used, the presence of bubbled gas, temperature, solvent composition and reaction volume ?

Sonocatalysis – Ultrasonically assisted catalysis

It is initiation of a catalytic reaction by irradiation with sound or ultrasound. The effects of ultrasonication are (to a large degree) results of the ultrasonic cavitation in liquids. Therefore, ultrasonically assisted catalysis requires at least one reagent to be in liquid phase. Ultrasound contributes to heterogeneous and homogeneous catalysis in many ways. The decomposition of water was performed using a sonocatalytic reaction system, which is a joint system of sonochemical and catalytical reactions by using homogeneous catalysts of Fe^{III} compounds²⁰⁶. Suslick and Casadonte²⁰⁷ reported heterogeneous sonocatalysis with nickel powder.

The synthesis of chalcones via Claisen-Schmidt condensation between benzaldehyde and acetophenone by

sonochemical and thermally activated reactions over a new type of zeolite as catalyst was reported²⁰⁸. In this green solvent free procedure, chalcones are selectively produced in very high yields (>95%) when cesium exchanged X-NH₂ is employed under ultrasound activation. Ultrasound has shown to increase the rate of the TEMPO-mediated oxidation of methyl α -D-glucopyranoside or sucrose in the presence of stoichiometric amounts of sodium hypochlorite in basic aqueous medium. The reaction can then occur without the usually necessary sodium bromide, showing that ultrasound acts at the level of the formation of the nitrosonium ion, the active oxidizing species in the carbohydrate²⁰⁹. Her *et al.*²¹⁰ described a comparative study of sonocatalytic enhancement for removal of bisphenol-A and 17 α -ethinyl estradiol. The sonocatalyzed ammonothermal technique has been developed for the preparation of lithium niobate fine powders from commercially as received niobium pentoxide and lithium nitrate²¹¹.

Ultrasound technology is applied as a recent and environment-friendly process in an increasing number of applications and processes of the chemical industry. Its remarkable application options are in pharmacy, chemistry, biotechnology and environmental engineering. The applications make use of different effects of ultrasound for the processing of gaseous, liquid and solid media. Moreover, ultrasound has a generally accelerating and favorable impact on heterogeneous reactions. Cavitation, which is the main sono-physical effect, enhances mass transfer and mechanical damage at solid-liquid interfaces. It brings about localized extremes of temperature, pressure and transient electric effect. Under these conditions the chemical processes manifest themselves in increased reaction rates, easier initiation, less extreme process conditions and changes in reaction selectivity.

Microwave assisted organic synthesis

In this environmental conscious era, the role of chemists²¹² is to develop processes and design products, which can either eliminate or minimize the generation of toxic by-products and other pollutants. This objective can be easily achieved to a reasonable extent through the development of aqueous synthetic protocols using microwave radiations. It is worthwhile to note that rapid development of "Green Organic Chemistry" is due to the recog-

nition that eco-friendly products and processes will be economical in the long term as these do not require treatment of "end-of-the-pipe" pollutants, and by-products so commonly generated by conventional synthetic procedures and one such technology is microwave assisted organic synthesis (MAOS)^{213,214}.

Microwave heating under controlled conditions is an invaluable technology because it not only dramatically reduces reaction times, typically from days or hours to minutes or even seconds, i.e. speed up the reaction, but it also fulfills the aim of green chemistry by reducing side reactions, increasing yields and improves reproducibility.

Microwaves as a tool for synthetic chemistry

Hull^{215,216} reported the earliest description of the magnetron (the high-power generator of microwave power), a diode with a cylindrical anode. The potential of microwave heating for organic synthesis has been explored in last two and half decades after the first reports appeared in 1986^{217,218}. Initially, reactions were performed in domestic microwave ovens using appropriate solvents. After that, several groups started investigating reactions in solvent free conditions including "dry media" usually with open vessels^{219,220}. Microwave induced organic reaction enhancement chemistry (MORE) has been described by Bose²²¹⁻²²⁴ as a safe and convenient alternative to pressure reactions in unmodified microwave ovens.

Classification of microwave reactions

Broadly microwave assisted organic synthesis can be classified into solvent assisted and solvent free synthesis.

Solvent assisted synthesis

Solvent assisted synthesis proceeds in the presence of solvent with good polarity, high boiling point and sufficient chemical stability. *N,N*-Dimethylformamide (DMF) is a good solvent for microwave assisted organic synthesis as it has a high boiling point (154 °C), high dielectric constant and is miscible with water, making it relatively easy to be removed from the reaction mixture. Bose *et al.*²²⁵ synthesized protected amino acid from tetrachlorophthalic anhydride and glycine using DMF as solvent to yield 300 g of the product within 8 min. A dramatic increase in the overall speed of peptide synthesis was

reported by Olivos *et al.*²²⁶. Hu *et al.*²²⁷ carried out substitution of nitro group in presence of tetrahydrofuran in good yields (83%).

Mehta *et al.*^{228,229} synthesized and characterized some pyridine and quinazoline derivatives under microwave irradiation as potent antimicrobial agents while Parashar *et al.*²³⁰ made a comparison between conventional and microwave assisted synthesis of some pyrazoline derivatives and their antimicrobial activity. Microwave assisted synthesis and characterization of some new annulated pyrimidinone derivatives has been done by Sancheti *et al.*²³¹.

Solvent free synthesis

Solvent free synthesis offers safe and efficient reaction pathways, which are time and money saving and often enable elimination of waste treatment. Solvent free syntheses are subdivided into solid support reactions and neat reactions.

Solid support reactions

Microwave assisted solid support reactions profoundly increases the rate of reactions and decrease the reaction time. It also gives high conversion with high selectivity, avoiding solvent in most of the cases and therefore, workup also becomes easier. Testero and Mata²³² reported synthesis of 3-(aryl)alkenyl- α -lactams by an efficient application of olefin cross-use of polymer supported organometallic catalysts in organic synthesis. KF-alumina-mediated Bargellini reaction has been reported by Rohman and Myrboh²³³.

Vyas *et al.*²³⁴ reported microwave assisted synthesis and biological assay of 2-substituted [(morpholin-4-yl)/4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)methyl]-1H-benzimidazoles using acidic alumina as solid support.

Neat reactions

Such reactions are performed between neat reagents. Here, at least one of reagent must be a polar liquid. Ameta

*et al.*²³⁵ reported solvent free synthesis of phthalimide derivatives under microwave irradiation. Microwave assisted one-pot synthesis of pyrazolone derivatives under solvent free conditions has been demonstrated by Ma *et al.*²³⁶.

LiBr has been used as a catalyst for solvent free synthesis of fused thiazoloquinazoline derivatives²³⁷. AlCl₃ has been used as a catalyst for microwave enhanced and solvent free green protocol for the production of dihydropyrimidine-2-(1H)-ones²³⁸.

Applications in organic synthesis

The microwave chemistry is the current approach in green chemistry, as it follows number of principles of green chemistry. Here some applications of microwave assisted organic synthesis are reported.

Microwave assisted oxidation reactions

Lukasiewicz *et al.*²³⁹ carried out microwave assisted oxidation of some aromatics by hydrogen peroxide at supported tungsten catalyst. A remarkably fast microwave assisted selective oxidation of benzylic alcohols with calcium hypochlorite under solvent free conditions has been reported²⁴⁰. Alcohols are readily adsorbed on clayfen and rapidly oxidized to corresponding carbonyl compounds upon exposure to microwaves under solvent free conditions.

Microwave assisted reduction reaction

Bose *et al.*^{241,242} were first to report the use of microwaves for transfer hydrogenation in organic synthesis. A series of β -lactam derivatives were hydrogenated using formates and Pd/C or Raney Ni as catalyst. Schmoeger *et al.*²⁴³ carried out microwave assisted reduction of organic compounds using catalytic and stoichiometric reactions. Microwave assisted reduction of carbonyl compounds in solid state using sodium borohydride supported on alumina has been studied by Varma and Saini²⁴⁴.

Microwave assisted alkylation

MW assisted selective *N*-alkylation of 6-amino-2-thiouracil in DMF using different alkyl halides has been investigated by Loupy *et al.*²⁴⁵ whereas no reaction was observed under the same conditions in a thermoregulated oil bath. Syntheses of *N*-alkyl phthalimides and *N*-alkyl succinimides have been reported on silica gel in dry media under MW and PTC conditions²⁴⁶.

Microwave assisted rearrangement

Loupy and Regnier²⁴⁷ compared Beckmann rearrangement of benzaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetophenones oximes by conventional and MW heating. They found that yields are significantly enhanced under microwave exposure.

Microwave assisted double decarboxylative Claisen rearrangement has been reported by Craig *et al.*²⁴⁸.

Microwave assisted cycloaddition

Microwave assisted Diels-Alder cycloaddition reaction between 2-fluoro-3-methoxy-1,3-butadiene and ethylene was studied by Patrick *et al.*²⁴⁹. Microwave assisted synthesis of a [3 + 2] cycloaddition library was studied by Wilson *et al.*²⁵⁰.

Microwave assisted condensation

Zaydi and Borik²⁵¹ performed microwave assisted

condensation reactions of 2-aryl hydrazonepropanals with dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate under solvent free conditions. Microwave assisted Knoevenagel condensation under solvent free conditions has been studied by Mallouk *et al.*²⁵² using hydroxyapatite as a catalyst and reported yield is high. Ighlahriz *et al.*²⁵³ synthesized 4(3*H*)-quinazolinones by cyclocondensation of anthranilic acid, aniline and orthoester (or formic acid) in presence of HPA as a catalyst under MWI.

Microwave assisted protection reaction

Microwave assisted selective protection of glutaraldehyde and its monoacetals and thioacetals was carried out by Flink *et al.*²⁵⁴. They reported that reactions proceed efficiently and only traces of deprotected materials were left.

Microwave assisted transition metal catalyzed coupling reactions

Microwave flash heating accelerate transition metal catalyzed homogeneous reactions including Heck coupling cross-coupling and asymmetric substitution²⁵⁵. Walla and Kappe²⁵⁶ carried out microwave assisted Negishi and Kumada cross-coupling reactions of aryl chlorides. Perbenzylated pyranoid glycals couples with aryl bromides under MWI in the presence of 5% mol palladium(II) acetate in DMF to produce 2',3'-unsaturated *C*-aryl-*d*-glycopyranosides in a rapid and stereospecific manner²⁵⁷.

Microwave assisted synthesis of heterocycles

The efficient use of MW heating approach in several organic synthesis as an emerging green technique has been proposed by several workers^{258,259}. Zhao *et al.*²⁶⁰ discovered a general microwave assisted protocol for the expedient synthesis of quinoxalines and heterocyclic pyrazines. The synthesis of pyrroles by reaction of hex-

ane-2,5-dione with primary amines has been carried out by Danks²⁶¹ under microwave irradiation.

Microwave assisted synthesis of nanocomposites

Wang and Lee²⁶² carried out microwave assisted synthesis of SnO₂-graphite nanocomposite for Li-ion battery applications. Polyacrylamide-metal nanocomposites with metal nanoparticles homogeneously dispersed in the polymer matrix have been successfully prepared using corresponding metal.

Microwave assisted synthesis of ionic liquids

A microwave assisted preparation of an ambient temperature ionic liquids, 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium halides via efficient reaction of 1-methylimidazole with alkyl halide under solvent-free conditions has been described by Varma and Nambodiri²⁶³. Khadilkar and Rebeiro²⁶⁴ reported the synthesis of various alkyl pyridinium and 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium halide under microwave exposure in a closed vessel.

Looking to the importance of MWI in synthetic chemistry, it can be concluded that time is not far off, when microwave heating technique will almost replace the conventional techniques, not only in laboratory but in industries also. They will truly become the Bunsen burner of the 21st century, but still there are rooms to investigate this field and to develop greener routes to synthesize other useful compounds for the benefit of mankind.

Ultimately, one can conclude that microwave mediated synthesis is a green chemical technology because microwave not only accelerate chemical processes but also improve yield, selectivity, reduces pollution and enable reactions to occur in solvent free conditions.

This article has highlighted the potential and scope of green chemistry for clean and sustainable development in brief; however, the field is still in its infant stage and therefore, success of green chemistry depends on the train-

ing and education of the new generation of chemists. Students, researchers and manufacturers have to be introduced at all levels to the philosophy and practice of green chemistry. This is the need of the day for achieving clean and sustainable development of any country in the world.

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